

Synthesis of Some New Arylnaphthoxazole : Sulphonamides, Sulphonic Esters and Thiosulphonic Esters. Part III.

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A number of 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonamides (II-IV), sulphonic esters (V-VII) and thiosulphonic esters (VIII-X) have been prepared by the interaction of 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonyl chloride (Ia-c) with different heterocyclic amines, phenols and thiols respectively. The biological activities of the prepared compounds were screened against some strains of bacteria.

THE remarkable biological activities of some oxazoles¹⁻³ has promoted us to synthesize new oxazolesulphonamides. It was thought that the combination of an oxazole ring with the well known chemotherapeutic sulphonamide substituents⁴⁻⁶ might increase these biological activities, and so the synthesis and structural elucidation of previously unknown aryl-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole sulphonamides, sulphonic esters and thiosulphonic esters were undertaken.

Experimental

Melting points reported were uncorrected. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer. The uv spectra in spec. pure ethanol were taken on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 ultraviolet spectrophotometer. Antibacterial activities were carried out by Dr. M. Atia, Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, Assiut University.

2-(Nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonylchloride (Ia-c) :

A mixture of dry 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonic acid^{7,8} (2 g.) and thionyl chloride (5 ml) was refluxed in presence of 2 drops of dimethyl formamide for about 2 hr. on a water bath. The excess thionyl chloride was evaporated and the residue washed with ether to give the crude sulphonyl chloride (Ia-c) which was extracted and recrystallized from dry benzene in about 60% yield. The results are as follows : (a) 2-(*o*-nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonyl chloride (Ia), m.p. 138° (Found : C, 52.38 ; H, 2.36 ; N, 7.00 ; S, 8.01 ; Cl, 8.86 ; C₁₇H₉N₂O₅SCl, Calculated : C, 52.50 ; H, 2.31 ; N, 7.20 ; S, 8.23 ; Cl, 9.13%). (b) 2-(*m*-nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonyl chloride (Ib), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 52.34 ; H, 2.26 ; N, 7.01 ; S, 8.41 ; Cl, 9.01 ; C₁₇H₉N₂O₅SCl ; Calculated : C, 52.50 ; H, 2.31 ; N, 7.20 ; S, 8.23 ; Cl, 9.13%). (c) 2-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonyl chloride (Ic), m.p. 221°

(Found : C, 52.23 ; H, 2.23 ; N, 6.98 ; S, 8.11 ; Cl, 8.92 ; C₁₇H₉N₂O₅SCl ; Calculated : C, 52.50 ; H, 2.31 ; N, 7.20 ; S, 8.23 ; Cl, 9.13 %).

2-(Nitrophenyl)-naphth[1,2-d] oxazole-5-(*N*-substituted sulphonamide) (II-III & IV) : A mixture of arylloxazole sulphonyl chloride (I ; 0.01 mole) and the appropriate heterocyclic amine (0.01 mole) (2-amino-pyridine, 3-aminopyridine, 2-amino-benzoxazole⁹, 2-aminobenzthiazole, 2-amino-4-phenyl-thiazole¹⁰ and 2-amino-4-(*p*-tolyl) thiazole¹⁰ in dry benzene (30 ml) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ as a catalyst was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into water (25 ml), the benzene layer was evaporated and the precipitate naphthoxazole sulphonamide was collected, washed well with ether and crystallized from *n*-butanol. The results are given in Table 1.

2-(Nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonic esters (V, VI & VII) and thiosulphonic esters (VIII, IX & X) : A mixture of arylloxazole sulphonyl chloride (I ; 0.01 mole) and the appropriate phenol (phenol, *p*-nitrophenol, *m*-cresol, α -naphthol and β -naphthol ; 0.01 mole) or thiol (thiophenol, 2-mercaptoimidazole¹¹, 2-mercaptobenzimidazole¹², 2-mercaptobenzoxazole¹³ and 2-mercaptanaphth [1,2-d] oxazole¹⁴ ; 0.01 mole) in dry benzene (40 ml) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ as a catalyst was refluxed on a water bath for 2.5-3 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated, whereby, the sulphonic ester (V, VI & VII) or the thiosulphonic ester (VIII, IX & X) was deposited, filtered off, washed well with ether and recrystallized from *n*-butanol. The results are given in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The present report deals with the preparation of new heterocyclic sulphonamides substituted on the sulphonamide nitrogen, since substituted derivatives are the only which have been reported.

Thus, 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonyl chlorides (Ia-c) were obtained by the

direct interaction of thionyl chloride with aryl-naphthoxazole sulphonic acids.

Naphthoxazole sulphonyl chlorides (Ia-c) were converted directly to N-substituted sulphonamides by its interaction with different heterocyclic amines such as, 2-aminopyridine, 3-aminopyridine, 2-aminobenzoxazole, 2-aminobenzthiazole, 2-amino-4-phenyl-thiazole and 2-amino-4-(*p*-tolyl)-thiazole, producing 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-(N-substituted sulphonamide) (II-IV). In this manner, a number of new types of heterocyclic sulphonamides have been prepared (Table 1). These compounds are quite stable and can be recrystallized from organic solvents. They are fairly resistant to hot 0.1 *N* hydrochloric acid and to hot 1*N* sodium hydroxide solution.

Naphthoxazole sulphonamides (II-IV) have been identified by a combination of elemental and spectral analysis. The IR spectra of compounds (II-IV) are characterised by an absorption band in the region of 1350-1340 cm^{-1} which attributed to the vibration of $-\text{SO}_2-\text{N}$ -group¹⁵, bands at 1625-1610, 1610-1590 & 1550-1540 cm^{-1} characterised the

oxazole system¹⁶ and band at 1530 cm^{-1} for the NO_2 group¹⁵. The uv spectra of sulphonamide compounds (III) showed λ_{max} near 280, 310 and 340 nm.

On the other hand, sulphonyl chlorides (Ia-c) were reacted with different phenols and thiol compounds in dry benzene and anhydrous K_2CO_3 , gave the corresponding products, 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-sulphonic esters (V-VII) and 2-(nitrophenyl)-naphth [1,2-d] oxazole-5-thio-sulphonic esters (VIII-X) respectively. (cf. Table 2). The IR spectra¹⁵ of compounds (V-VII), showed, vibration bands at 1420-1400 cm^{-1} and 1190-1160 cm^{-1} characterised the $-\text{O}-\text{SO}_2$ -group and of compounds (VIII-X) showed two intense bands near 1340 cm^{-1} and 1150 cm^{-1} for $-\text{S}-\text{SO}_2$ -group.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(NITROPHENYL)-NAPHTH[1,2-d]OXAZOLE-5-(N-SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDES) (II, III & IV)

Compound No.	R	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis (Calc./Found)%			
				C	H	N	S
IIa	Pyridine-2	217-8	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.19	3.13	12.55	7.17
				58.86	3.01	12.34	7.02
IIb	Pyridine-3	285-6	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.19	3.13	12.55	7.17
				58.91	3.11	12.40	6.98
IIc	Benzoxazole-2	180-3	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.25	2.88	11.52	6.58
				59.11	2.68	11.41	6.32
IId	Benzthiazole-2	170-1	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	57.37	2.78	11.15	12.74
				57.22	2.62	11.01	12.56
IIe	4-phenyl-thiazole-2	152-3	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.09	3.03	10.60	12.12
				59.13	3.11	10.52	12.36
IIIf	4-(<i>p</i> -tolyl)-thiazole-2	187-8	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.77	3.32	10.33	11.80
				59.67	3.28	10.24	11.72
IIIa	Pyridine-2	278	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.19	3.13	12.55	7.17
				59.03	3.01	12.46	7.31
IIIb	Pyridine-3	281	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.19	3.13	12.55	7.17
				59.11	3.21	12.43	7.22
IIIc	Benzoxazole-2	178-80	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.25	2.88	11.52	6.58
				59.03	2.71	11.38	6.38
IIId	Benzthiazole-2	220	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	57.37	2.78	11.15	12.74
				57.16	2.61	11.02	12.53
IIIe	4-phenyl-thiazole-2	193	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.09	3.03	10.60	12.12
				59.16	3.03	10.42	12.30
IIIIf	4-(<i>p</i> -tolyl)-thiazole-2	>350	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.77	3.32	10.33	11.80
				59.63	3.13	10.21	11.62
IVa	Pyridine-2	298	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.19	3.13	12.55	7.17
				59.31	3.20	12.45	7.02
IVb	Pyridine-3	278	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.19	3.13	12.55	7.17
				58.87	3.01	12.31	7.41
IVc	Benzoxazole-2	>350	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	59.25	2.88	11.52	6.58
				59.00	2.68	11.41	6.31
IVd	Benzthiazole-2	232	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	57.37	2.78	11.15	12.74
				57.01	2.67	11.04	12.31
IVe	4-phenyl-thiazole-2	165-8	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.09	3.03	10.60	12.12
				59.31	2.89	10.43	11.79
IVf	4-(<i>p</i> -tolyl)-thiazole-2	>300	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.77	3.32	10.33	11.80
				59.42	3.33	10.12	11.63

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(NITROPHENYL)-NAPHTH[1,2-d]OXAZOLE-5-SULPHONIC ESTERS (V, VI & VII) AND THIOSULPHONIC ESTERS (VIII, IX & X)

Compound No.	R	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	Analysis (Calc./Found)%			
				C	H	N	S
Va	Phenyl	129	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	61.88	3.13	6.27	7.17
				61.63	3.02	6.01	7.31
Vb	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	122	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	56.21	2.64	8.55	6.51
				56.11	2.56	8.48	6.43
Vc	<i>m</i> -tolyl	150	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S	62.60	3.47	6.08	6.95
				62.42	3.41	5.81	6.81
VIa	Phenyl	122	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	61.88	3.13	6.27	7.17
				61.63	3.08	6.13	7.29
VIb	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	128	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	56.21	2.64	8.55	6.51
				56.32	2.59	8.43	6.42
VIc	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	136	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S	62.60	3.47	6.08	6.95
				62.40	3.34	6.31	6.67
VIId	α -Naphthyl	135-7	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₆ S	65.32	3.22	5.64	6.45
				65.08	3.21	5.48	6.31
VIe	β -Naphthyl	140	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₆ S	65.32	3.22	5.64	6.45
				65.41	3.17	5.55	6.32
VIIa	Phenyl	132	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S	61.88	3.13	6.27	7.17
				61.76	3.06	6.02	7.00
VIIb	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	207	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₆ S	56.21	2.64	8.55	6.51
				56.01	2.61	8.43	6.28
VIIIa	Imidazoline-2	165	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	52.86	3.08	12.33	14.09
				52.71	3.01	12.13	14.31
VIIIb	Naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2	170-3	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	60.75	2.71	7.59	11.57
				60.56	2.63	7.41	11.48
IXa	Phenyl	115	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	59.74	3.03	6.03	13.85
				59.63	3.11	5.89	13.65
IXb	Imidazoline-2	148	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	52.86	3.08	12.33	14.09
				52.76	3.01	12.34	13.87
IXc	Benzimidazole-2	123	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	57.37	2.78	11.15	12.74
				57.18	2.67	11.01	12.48
IXd	Benzoxazole-2	158-60	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	57.25	2.58	8.34	12.72
				57.01	2.47	8.23	12.65
IXe	Naphth[1,2-d]oxazole-2	185-6	C ₂₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	60.75	2.71	7.59	11.57
				60.61	2.66	7.48	11.42
X	Phenyl	170	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	59.74	3.03	6.03	13.85
				59.43	3.11	5.87	13.68

 V; *o*-NO₂
 VI; *m*-NO₂
 VII; *p*-NO₂

 VIII; *o*-NO₂
 IX; *m*-NO₂
 X; *p*-NO₂

expressed in percent range from 40 to 75% inhibition was found at concentration $10^{-3} M$.

The more strong active compounds against *Staph. aureus*, *Mycobacterium phlei* and *Bacillus subtilis* are (IIb, IIc, IIe, IVd, IVe, VIIb & X) and against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus morganii* and *E. coli* are (IId, IIe, IIIe & IVd) respectively.

Antimicrobial activities :

The antimicrobial activities of the prepared sulphonamides, sulphonic esters and thiosulphonic esters against a variety of microbes were determined¹⁷. These micro-organisms include Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The bacteria used are :

Bacillus subtilis, *Staph. aureus*, *Mycobacterium phlei*, *Proteus morganii*, *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

The results showed that most of the prepared compounds (II, IV, V, VII, VIII & X) show from a little to a strong activity on the Gram-positive and the Gram-negative bacteria. The activity

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